

Achieving Low Carbon Environment over Technological Innovation and Collaboration in New Energy Vehicle Supply Chains

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Abstract

In the context of a low-carbon environment, this study focuses on a three-tier supply chain for new energy vehicles (NEVs), consisting of raw material suppliers, vehicle manufacturers, and retailers. It explores the issue of emissions reduction through technological innovation and collaboration within the supply chain, considering the dynamics of carbon levels and product reputation. Based on the technological innovation collaboration of supply chain enterprises, a differential game model for centralized, decentralized, and revenue-sharing and cost-sharing contracts is constructed. The study seeks to solve the technological innovation game strategies under these three scenarios and uses numerical analysis to explore the coordination effects of contracts on the supply chain. The research provides a theoretical basis for dynamic coordination in technological innovation and emissions reduction in the NEV supply chain. The findings suggest that a centralized technological innovation game effectively optimizes the decisions and profits of supply chain members. The higher the technological innovation level, the more beneficial it is for enterprises to gain higher profits. Revenue-sharing and cost-sharing contracts can effectively coordinate technological innovation collaboration for emissions reduction, achieving a Pareto improvement in the profits of supply chain members and the system as a whole.

Keywords: *Low-carbon environment, new energy vehicle, supply chain, technological innovation.*

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Introduction

In October 2021, the state council of China issued the “Action Plan for Carbon Peak before 2030”, emphasizing the need to accelerate the green and low-carbon transformation in the manufacturing sector, striving to achieve the carbon peak target ahead of schedule (Xing, et al., 2024; Fang, & Li, 2024; Shoukat, et al., 2022). Against this backdrop, NEVs, due to their low-carbon and environmentally friendly characteristics, have received strong support from the government and have become widely favored by consumers. This has led to new development opportunities, with continuous innovations in green technologies (Xu, 2023). The NEV industry has gradually evolved from the “market introduction stage” to the “growth stage”.

The NEV supply chain involves numerous upstream and downstream enterprises, including vehicle manufacturers, suppliers, and retailers (Muhammad, Kerbache, & Elomri, 2022; Shoukat, et al., 2024; Rani, et al., 2024). In this entire process, it has become an inevitable trend for the NEV supply chain to cooperate in low-carbon technological innovations to gain competitive advantages. This collaboration is an effective approach and an important measure to promote the low-carbon transformation of energy-intensive products.

Many research has been done about low-carbon emissions reduction in supply chains from different perspectives. Regarding consumer low-carbon preferences, Song et al. (2024) has explored the impact of consumer low-carbon preferences on emissions reduction and profits in supply chain enterprises. In terms of technological innovation, Hong et al. (2024) studied the impact of different subsidy models for government support on enterprise profits in the context of green technology innovation. Huo et al. (2024) investigated the evolutionary paths of low-carbon innovation and emissions reduction in supply chains through evolutionary game theory. From a dynamic emissions reduction perspective, Cheng et al. (2024) used differential game theory to consider the dynamics of emission reductions and studied reduction strategies under different cooperation scenarios. Zhang et al. (2020) explored the emissions reduction levels and green investment issues in supply chain enterprises by considering brand reputation and greenness as state variables.

In the area of supply chain contract coordination, scholars have designed various contracts to facilitate cooperation for emissions reduction in the supply chain. Yang et al. (2022) has constructed three different cost-sharing model frameworks, comparing the equilibrium solutions of different models in terms of greenness and profit. Qin et al. (2021) developed a positive distribution function to analyze carbon emission reduction strategies in green supply chains based on cost-sharing and designed cost-sharing contracts to coordinate carbon reduction decision-making within the supply chain. Xu et al. (2012) built models for suppliers, manufacturers, and retailers who are dependent on carbon emissions and engaged in low-carbon emissions reduction and low-carbon publicity. These models include scenarios with no cost-sharing, sharing sales costs, sharing emission reduction costs, and splitting both, in order to study the emissions reduction strategies under different contract models.

In instantaneous, previous study have researched the issue of cooperative emissions reduction in low-carbon supply chains from various viewpoints. However, there is limited research that involves the three-tier NEV supply chain and analyzes the emissions reduction process in a low-carbon supply chain from the dynamic perspective of technological innovation collaboration. Therefore, this paper, based on the low-carbon environment and considering the dynamics of carbon levels and product reputation, employs differential game theory to build decentralized, centralized, and contract models. It dynamically studies the low-carbon technological innovation cooperation and emissions reduction decisions within the three-tier NEV supply chain, consisting of suppliers,

manufacturers, and retailers, providing a reference for low-carbon technological innovation cooperation in NEV supply chain enterprises.

Problem Statement and Methodology

Problem Statement

Assume that the NEV supply chain consists of a raw material supplier, vehicle manufacturers, and retailers, as shown in Figure 1. The supplier increases technological innovation to process raw materials in a low-carbon manner and provides low-carbon components to the manufacturer. The manufacturer, through low-carbon technology, improves production processes to produce low-carbon products. At the same time, retailers innovate marketing strategies to promote low-carbon initiatives, collectively addressing the market environment. The manufacturer, as the leader in the supply chain, plays an important role in the technological innovation cooperation process within the NEV supply chain. Based on the cooperation between enterprises, three scenarios are designed: decentralized, centralized, and revenue-sharing with cost-sharing contracts (referred to as: contracts).

Figure 1. Supply Chain Structure of New Energy Vehicles

Model Assumptions

Assume that at time t , the raw material supplier and vehicle manufacturer's average low-carbon technological innovation levels are represented by $X_s(t)$ and $X_m(t)$, respectively. The retailer's average low-carbon promotion level is represented by $X_r(t)$. Due to the technological innovation costs and the cost of low-carbon promotion being functionally dependent, the costs are considered as fixed functions (Hong, et al., 2024; Zhang, Guo, & Wang, 2020), without considering other cost factors. Therefore, the raw material supplier's technological innovation cost and the manufacturer's low-carbon promotion cost are separately represented as:

$$\begin{cases} C_s(X_s(t)) = \frac{k_s}{2} (X_s(t))^2 \\ C_m(X_m(t)) = \frac{k_m}{2} (X_m(t))^2 \\ C_r(X_r(t)) = \frac{k_r}{2} (X_r(t))^2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where, k_s, k_m , and $k_r > 0$ are the cost coefficients of technological innovation for suppliers and manufacturers, and the cost coefficients of low-carbon promotion for distributors, respectively.

Manufacturers and suppliers produce low-carbon products through low-carbon technology innovation, and low-carbon products naturally decay (Zhang, Guo, & Wang, 2020). Therefore, the low-carbon level can be characterized as $\dot{L}(t) = \alpha X_s(t) + \beta X_m(t) - \gamma L(t)$, where, $\alpha (\alpha > 0)$ is the impact coefficient of the supplier's low-carbon technology innovation level on the low-carbon level. The $\beta (\beta > 0)$ is the impact coefficient of the manufacturer's low-carbon technology innovation level on the low-carbon level. The $\gamma (\gamma > 0)$ is the attenuation coefficient of the low-carbon level. The initial low-carbon level of the product is as:

$$L(0) = L_0 \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

Distributors use low-carbon promotion to enhance product reputation, which affects the profits of the entire supply chain and is also affected by natural decay. Therefore, product reputation can be characterized as $\dot{G}(t) = \eta X_r(t) - \mu G(t)$. The $\eta (\eta > 0)$ represents the impact coefficient of low-carbon promotion level on product reputation, and $\mu (\mu > 0)$ denotes the attenuation coefficient of product reputation. The $G(t) = G_0 \geq 0$ is the initial product reputation.

According to Esmaeeli, Mollaverdi, & Safarzadeh, (2024), the purchase price of low-carbon components and the sales price of low-carbon products are functions of wholesale price. Let $P_s(t) = \varepsilon_1 \omega(t)$ and $P_r(t) = \varepsilon_2 \omega(t)$, where, $P_s(t)$, $\omega(t)$ and $P_r(t)$ represent the purchase price, wholesale price, and sales price, respectively. The $0 < \varepsilon_1 < 1$ is supplier price markup coefficient, and $\varepsilon_2 > 1$ is the retailer price markup coefficient.

Based on the characterization of demand function in Aliabadi, et al. (2024), consumers tend to prefer products with low prices, low carbon emissions, and high reputation. According to Yang, et al. (2022), the demand function is influenced by both price and non-price factors, and can be separated through multiplication. Therefore, this article represents the demand function of low-carbon products as:

$$D(t) = [D_0 - \lambda P_r(t)] \times [\theta L(t) + \delta G(t)] \quad (3)$$

where, $D_0 > 0$ signifies potential market demand and $\lambda > 0$ represents price elasticity coefficient. The $\theta > 0$ and $\delta > 0$ represent the sensitivity coefficients of low-carbon level and product reputation to demand, respectively.

Suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors have the same discount rate $\rho (\rho > 0)$ at any time and make decisions based on complete information. Therefore, the long-term profit function of suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors is π_s, π_m and π_r .

Comparative Analysis

This section compares and analyzes the equilibrium strategies and profits under the three decision-making scenarios mentioned above, and then analyzes the effectiveness of contract design. At the same time, some inferences are drawn based on the equilibrium strategy. The relationship between

the low-carbon technology innovation level of suppliers and manufacturers and the low-carbon promotion level of distributors under different decision-making scenarios is as follows:

$$X_s^D = X_s^C > X_s^Y \quad (4)$$

$$X_m^C = X_m^Y > X_m^D \quad (5)$$

$$X_r^C = X_r^Y > X_r^D \quad (6)$$

Compared with the dispersed situation, the low-carbon level and reputation of products under the contract are effectively improved, and the relationship is as follows:

$$L_\infty^C > L_\infty^Y > L_\infty^D \quad (7)$$

$$G_\infty^C = G_\infty^Y > G_\infty^D \quad (8)$$

Above equations (4-8) indicate that under decentralized decision-making, the decision-making level of all parties in the supply chain is the lowest, and they make their own decisions for the maximization of their own interests, resulting in a double marginal effect. This weakens the low-carbon technology innovation of suppliers and manufacturers, as well as the low-carbon promotion motivation of distributors. However, under the contract, the low-carbon technology innovation level of manufacturers and the low-carbon promotion level of distributors are effectively improved, reaching a centralized level. Moreover, the low-carbon level and product reputation under the contract have been improved. This indicates that the contract promotes close cooperation among supply chain members, optimizes internal resources, improves balance strategies, and also achieves the transformation of low-carbon production, bringing environmental benefits.

Under the three decision-making scenarios, the low-carbon technology innovation level of suppliers is positively correlated with parameters such as θ and α (dispersion and contract scenarios are also positively correlated with ε_1), and negatively correlated with λ , ρ , γ , k_s , and ε_2 . The low-carbon technology innovation level of manufacturers is positively correlated with parameters such as θ and β , and negatively correlated with λ , ρ , γ and k_m (dispersion and contract situations are also negatively correlated with ε_1 and ε_2). The low-carbon promotion level of dealers is positively correlated with parameters such as δ and η (dispersion and contract situation are also positively correlated with ε_2), and negatively correlated with λ , ρ , μ and k_r . Its indicates that when demand is more sensitive to low-carbon levels or low-carbon levels are more sensitive to innovation levels, suppliers and manufacturers are more motivated to engage in low-carbon technology innovation. The higher the cost of technological innovation, the easier it is for innovative equipment to age, or the greater the price elasticity coefficient, the less motivation suppliers and manufacturers have for low-carbon technological innovation. When demand is more sensitive to product reputation or product reputation is more sensitive to promotional level, distributors are more motivated to carry out low-carbon promotion; The higher the cost of low-carbon promotion, the lower the

effectiveness of low-carbon promotion, or the greater the price elasticity coefficient, the less motivation for dealers to carry out low-carbon promotion.

In decentralized and contractual situations, the larger the price markup coefficient ε_1 , the more it can promote suppliers' investment in low-carbon technology innovation, but it will reduce manufacturers' enthusiasm for low-carbon technology innovation. The larger the price markup coefficient ε_2 , the more it can improve the low-carbon promotion level of distributors. However, excessively high sales prices can affect the reputation of low-carbon products, thereby affecting the enthusiasm of suppliers for low-carbon technology innovation and causing manufacturers to reduce their investment in low-carbon technology innovation.

Numerical Analysis

To verify the effectiveness of technological innovation in the NEV supply chain under a low-carbon environment, we analyze the optimal strategies and profits under different decision-making models, and perform a sensitivity analysis on the key factors. According to Junhua, Yue, & Fu, (2022), the parameters used in the analysis are $\rho = 0.9$, $D_0 = 20$, $\lambda = 1$, $\theta = 0.8$, $\delta = 0.8$, $\alpha = 0.6$, $\beta = 0.6$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mu = 0.2$, $k_s = 24$, $k_m = 20$, $k_r = 10$, $\varepsilon_1 = 0.8$, and $\varepsilon_2 = 1.3$.

Comparison of Optimal Results

Using the parameters mentioned above, we compare the results under different models: decentralized (D), centralized (C), and contract (Y), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Equilibrium Results under Different Decision-Making Scenarios

Model	X_s^*	X_m^*	X_r^*	ω^*	λ_1^*	λ_2^*	L_∞^C	G_∞^C
D	1.6	0.4	1.3	6.2	—	—	15.3	5.4
C	2.7	2.4	5.8	6.2	—	—	35.7	23.3
Y	1.6	2.4	5.8	6.2	0.1	0.8	27.5	23.3

From Table 1, it can be seen that, while the price remains the same across all scenarios, the equilibrium results in the centralized decision-making scenario (C) are significantly higher than in the decentralized decision-making scenario (D). Compared to the D model, in the Y model, the manufacturer's technological innovation level, the dealer's low-carbon promotion level, and product reputation all show substantial improvements, with increases of 549%, 334%, and 333%, respectively, reaching the levels seen in the centralized scenario. While the low-carbon level also increased by 79%, it did not reach the centralized level. This is because the revenue-sharing and cost-sharing contract enhanced the manufacturer's technological innovation level but had limited effects on the supplier's technological innovation level. Nevertheless, it strengthened the collaborative innovation and emissions reduction efforts within the supply chain enterprises.

Further analysis of the profits of supply chain enterprises under different decision-making scenarios reveals that, as shown in Figure 2, the overall supply chain profit under the C and Y models is significantly higher than under the D scenario. The design of the contract increased the levels of technological innovation investment and technological promotion, thereby improving the low-carbon level and product reputation. These two factors, as key indicators of the demand function, significantly boosted the overall profit of the supply chain. Furthermore, under the Y model, the profits of the supplier, manufacturer, and dealer are all higher than in the decentralized decision-making scenario. Therefore, the contract not only optimizes the overall benefit of the

supply chain but also encourages the supply chain members to strengthen cooperation, leverage their own advantages, and ensure long-term benefits for each enterprise.

Figure 2. Changes in Supply Chain Profits Over Time under Different Scenarios

Optimal Trajectory Analysis

Explore the optimal trajectory changes of low-carbon level and product reputation over time under different decision-making scenarios, as shown in Figures 3 and 4. In the three different modes, the trends of low-carbon level and product reputation are the same, and the curves all rise over time and eventually remain stable.

Figure 3. Optimal Trajectory for Low-Carbon Level

Figure 4. Optimal Trajectory of Product Reputation

Specifically, under the contract, the increase in the low-carbon level and product reputation is more rapid, and the product reputation reaches the centralized level. This is because, under this contract, the supply chain members strengthen collaboration and achieve resource sharing, which incentivizes the manufacturer to invest in technological innovation and the dealer to invest in technological promotion, thereby improving the technological innovation level. This also reflects that in the process of technological innovation cooperation within the NEV supply chain, it is not only necessary for upstream enterprises to innovate technologically and provide low-carbon products, but also for downstream enterprises to innovate in marketing techniques and increase promotion efforts, thereby enhancing the product's low-carbon level and reputation, and ultimately gaining greater market benefits.

Impact of Price Analysis

As the improvement effect of the revenue-sharing and cost-sharing contract in coordinating the supply chain is related to the price markup coefficient, this section analyzes the impact of the price markup coefficient on the profits of supply chain members, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The Impact of ϵ_1 on Profits under Different Scenarios

From Figure 5, it can be seen that under both the decentralized and contract scenarios, the profits of the supplier and dealer increase with the increase in the price markup coefficient ε_1 , and the profit increase for the supplier is more significant. For the supplier, the profit under the contract is significantly higher than under the decentralized model. For the manufacturer, the profit under the decentralized model decreases continuously as ε_1 increases, while the profit under the contract is not sensitive to changes in ε_1 . The two profit curves intersect at point A. When $\varepsilon_1 > 0.75$, and $\pi_m^Y > \pi_m^D$. For the dealer, $\pi_r^Y > \pi_r^D$, and the difference between the two gradually increases. In summary, ε_1 has a more significant impact on the supplier's profit. To ensure that all supply chain members accept the contract, the profits of all members under the contract should be higher than in the decentralized scenario. Therefore, ε_1 must satisfy $0.75 < \varepsilon_1 < 1$.

In both the decentralized and contract models, the dealer's profit significantly increases as the price markup coefficient ε_2 increases. The supplier's profit, on the other hand, decreases with the increase in ε_2 . In the decentralized scenario, the manufacturer's profit decreases as ε_2 increases, while in the contract scenario, the manufacturer's profit increases with ε_2 . In instant, ε_2 has a more significant impact on the dealer's profit. To ensure that all supply chain members accept the contract, the profits of all members under the contract must be higher than in the decentralized scenario.

Conclusion

This paper, set within a low-carbon context, examines the decision-making problem of technological innovation cooperation and emissions reduction within the three-tier NEV supply chain under three different scenarios. The low-carbon raw material procurement price, low-carbon product wholesale price, and sales price are the same under different decision-making modes. The technological innovation cooperation decisions under centralized and contract scenarios are significantly higher than those under the decentralized scenario. The optimal trajectory of low-carbon levels and product reputation under different decision-making models monotonically increases over time and tends to stabilize. Under certain conditions, the design of the contract incentivizes enterprises to invest in low-carbon technological innovation and promotion, promoting resource sharing among supply chain members, strengthening cooperation, leveraging each other's advantages, and raising the low-carbon level, which improves the product reputation to the centralized level. The contract can effectively improve the optimal profits of the supplier, manufacturer, and dealer, achieving Pareto improvements in the supply chain's profits. However, the improvement effect is related to the price markup coefficient. Under the conditions $0.75 < \varepsilon_1 < 1$ and $1.23 < \varepsilon_1 < 1.68$, all supply chain members will accept the contract, maintaining long-term technological innovation cooperation among supply chain enterprises and optimizing the supply chain. Therefore, in the automotive industry cluster supply chain, not only do upstream suppliers and manufacturers need to innovate technologically to produce low-carbon products, but retailers must also innovate marketing strategies to enhance product reputation.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest.

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